

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

D3.2 BIOcean5D Data Hub

Co-funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement number	101059915
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-0
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA
Project title	MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL AND HUMAN SCALES
Project acronym	BIOcean5D
Deliverable title	BIOcean5D Data Hub
Deliverable number	D3.2
Version	v1.0
Document status	Draft
Type	Data - Data sets, microdata etc.
Diffusion	PU - Public
Related Work Package	WP3 Data to knowledge, a digital foundation for holistic marine biodiversity assessment
Task	T3.2
Full lead beneficiary	EMBL - European Molecular Biology Laboratory
Author(s) and Affiliations	Ivica Letunic (Biobyte), Matej Trojak (EMBL), Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI), Kerstin Leberecht (EMBL), Peer Bork (EMBL), Pier Luigi Buttigieg (AWI), Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Leen Vandepitte (VLIZ), Lynn Delgat (VLIZ), Jean-Olivier Irisson (SU)
Project Officer	Victoria Beaz Hidalgo
Due date	M18 - 31.05.2024
Submission date	31.05.2024
Total number of pages	21
Keywords	Data flow concept, metadata templates, technical details, web interface, data submission, data security

Table of content

Table of content	3
Version history	4
List of Acronyms	5
Executive summary	7
1. Introduction	8
2. The technical details	10
2.1 Web interface	10
3. The BIOcean5D Data Hub - a sharing platform and connecting node	13
4. The data submission into the hub	15
5. Data security and access	18
Annexes	19

Version history

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Ivica Letunic (Biobyte), Kerstin Leberecht (EMBL), Matej Trojak (EMBL), Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Initial draft	20.03.2024
0.2	Stéphane Pesant (EMBL), Pier Luigi Buttigieg (AWI), Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Peer Bork (EMBL), Jean-Olivier Irisson (SU), Lynn Delgat (VLIZ), Leen Van de Pitte (VLIZ)	Review and input to initial draft	18.05.2024
0.3	Ivica Letunic (Biobyte), Kerstin Leberecht (EMBL), Matej Trojak (EMBL), Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Review, layout formatting, abbreviation and references lists	21.05.2024
0.4	Kerstin Leberecht (EMBL), Matej Trojak (EMBL), Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Including the feedback, layout formatting	29.05.2024

List of Acronyms

BioSamples	EBI database storing and supplying descriptions and metadata about biological samples used in research and development by academia and industry
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest
DMP	Data Management Plan
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
EcoTaxa	Web application dedicated to the visual exploration and the taxonomic identification of images of plankton
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EurOBIS	European node of the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IP	Intellectual Property
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
MetaboLights	EBI database for Metabolomics experiments and derived information
MGNify	EBI Microbiome analysis resource
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Observation System
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
PANGAEA	Publishing Network for Geoscientific and Environmental Data
PDB	Protein Data Bank
PID	Persistent Identifier
QC	Quality Control
SFTP	Secure file transfer protocols
TREC	TRaversing European Coastline
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is the first edition of the BIOcean5D data hub deliverable, which will undergo iterative enhancements throughout the project's life cycle in order to document major advancements towards the adoption of the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles that underpin the project's data ethos.

Within this deliverable, we delineate the objectives, technical architecture, organizational framework, operational modalities, and the present phase of the data hub's inception, alongside envisaged future refinements. As BIOcean5D evolves, it is anticipated to generate and circulate a progressively expanding corpus of data among consortium members, highlighting a collaborative and data-driven approach to advancing biodiversity research. This document articulates our commitment to establishing a robust infrastructure that not only facilitates data sharing and enhances research capabilities but also aligns with global standards in data stewardship, thereby contributing to the broader scientific discourse on biodiversity preservation.

1. Introduction

The BIOcean5D project is at the forefront of advancing the integration and distribution of a diverse array of (meta)data, crucial for enhancing the understanding and preservation of biodiversity. The cornerstone of our strategy is the development of the BIOcean5D data hub, a sophisticated platform designed to streamline the project's handling of multi-method and multi-stream biodiversity data.

BIOcean5D's primary goal is to facilitate seamless data sharing and integration within the project consortium, setting a solid foundation for subsequent dissemination to the broader scientific community. The data hub is engineered to provide a scalable, secure environment for data storage and distribution, thereby enabling efficient downstream analyses and fostering collaborative research efforts.

Recognizing the complex, heterogeneous nature of the project's data, WP3 is committed to evaluate and optimize the hardware and software frameworks that underpin our data flow and management processes. This includes deploying scalable database management systems that can adeptly integrate information from varied sources, ensuring the robustness and agility of our data handling capabilities.

As described in the Deliverable D3.1 - Initial Data Management Plan (DMP), the data hub's initial use will focus on internal data dissemination across various work packages (WPs), paving the way for the eventual release of data to public platforms. In detailing the scientific data flow, we outline the types of data produced, reused, and shared within the project, along with their respective (meta)data requirements, sources, and the technical specifications of the data hub infrastructure. Later, BIOcean5D's goal is to transform the data hub into an open-access platform that centralizes and provides all digital assets of the project to the broad scientific community. This initiative adheres to international standards concerning metadata, formatting, and taxonomical references, facilitating data transfer to long-term repositories like OBIS and EMODnet Biology. The project leverages the expertise of partners in data standardization, curation, and archiving (e.g., MGnify, ENA). This approach ensures the project's outputs are systematically organized, preserved, and made accessible, supporting the broader scientific community and contributing to the sustainable management of ocean resources.

This document presents the inaugural version of our data hub deliverable, which is poised for continual updates throughout the project lifecycle. These updates will reflect ongoing

developments, emerging opportunities, and our commitment to enhancing the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of BIOcean5D data. As the project evolves, more BIOcean5D data will be generated and shared within the consortium, underlining our dedication to fostering a collaborative, data-driven approach to biodiversity research.

2. The technical details

The initial version of the data hub was created as planned, providing storage for metadata, processed datasets and other data tied through a relational database. To ensure standards compliance and smooth flow of data among partners, data models in the repository will follow the JSON-LD/schema.org standards, which will be adjusted and extended as required during the project. Several access methods to the repository are provided, including the initial version of the web interface, allowing simple access to the data.

The data hub was physically set up at EMBL, and will be accessible through various access protocols via domain name bioceans5d.embl.de. As the main entry point for the partners, an internal web server was created, and is accessible at <https://bioceans5d.embl.de>. In addition to the main web interface, data exchange will be possible through secure file transfer protocols (SFTP) and other types of API access.

2.1 Web interface

The data hub uses an independent user account system, and anonymous access is not available at this stage of the project. Initially, several main areas of the data hub web interface have been developed (see Figures 1-3). A dedicated area is available for sharing various documents, experimental protocols, presentations and spreadsheets. Partners can freely upload and share project related files. An automatic notification system informs all users when a new file is uploaded.

Download documents and protocols

Upload Delete Search:

Date	User	Title	Description	File
2024-04-02	Ivica Letunic (Administrators)	BIOCEAN5D DOW	Main description of work for the project	BIOCEANS_5D_DOW.pdf
2024-04-02	Ivica Letunic (Administrators)	PR1: ITEMS TO COMPLETE WP2	PERIODIC REPORTING - LIST OF ITEMS TO COMPLETE	PR1-ListofItemstoComplete_WP2.docx
2024-04-02	Ivica Letunic (Administrators)	Dataset upload metadata template	List of required and optional metadata for dataset upload	BIOCEAN5D_dataset_upload_metadata_template.xlsx

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 files Previous 1 Next

Figure 1: The data hub's web interface showing the availability of BIOcean5D documents. Via the upload function, new documents can be shared in the data hub.

Datasets

filter... Show 10 datasets Search:

Category

- Location
 - Case study (84)
 - Global (60)
 - Non-georeferenced (279)
 - Regional (41)
 - TREC station (137)
 - Tara station (118)
 - Time-series station (97)
- Temporal range
- Temporal resolution
- Depth range
- License
- Work package
- Data type**
 - Acoustics (79)
 - Amplicon (123)
 - Environmental data (53)
 - Imaging data (180)
 - Metagenomic data (122)
 - Modelling data (34)
 - Remote sensing (73)
 - Socio-economic data (34)
 - Spatial data products (32)
 - Theory (40)
 - Traditional data (46)
- Search vocabulary
- Source

Dataset name	Description	Data silo	Taxonomy
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Amphipoda	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Amphipoda
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Appendicularia	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Appendicularia
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Chaetognatha	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Chaetognatha
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Coccolithophores	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Coccolithophores
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Copepoda	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Copepoda
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Diatoms	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Diatoms
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Dinoflagellates	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Dinoflagellates
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Euphausiacea	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Euphausiacea
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Foraminifera	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Foraminifera
AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Jellyfish	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset	microbiome	Jellyfish

1 to 10 of 816 datasets Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 82 Next

Figure 2: The data hub's web interface displays the availability of BIOcean5D data sets. The data hub is meticulously organized, featuring a navigation panel on the left-hand side that allows users to efficiently search for specific data.

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Dataset information		Back to overview		
Dataset name:	AtlantECO-BASE-V1-Amphipoda			
Description:	AtlantECO base microbiota dataset			
Contact:	Vogt Meike (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch)			
Data silo:	microbiome			
Taxonomy:	Amphipoda			
Details				
Category:	Data → Data set			
Location:	Global			
Temporal range:	Historic (multiple years)			
Temporal resolution:	Individual sampling dates			
Depth range:	Depth resolved			
License:	CC-BY-4.0			
B5D Workpackage:	WP3			
Data type:	Traditional data → Microscopy, nets, CPR			
Search vocabulary:	Biological oceanography → Microbiome Biological oceanography → Zooplankton			
Source:	B5D Partners → ETHZ Other → Global data repositories Other → Multiple (data synthesis)			
Downloads and links				
File name	Data type/variable	File type	Size	MD5 checksum
AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Amphipoda_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz	abund+biomass	data file	40Mb	05ec03693cf248537504baba6461b229
AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Amphipoda_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz	ind-carbon-values	data file	238Kb	3a9e344cb7cb63a422c63905c7551aff
[README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Amphipoda_abundance_biomass.docx	abund+biomass	README	555Kb	693648bacef74ad6c7a72a4720f3ddfe

Figure 3: Each data set is supplemented with metadata and categorized into specific data classes, enabling users to locate and utilize the information/data effectively.

A basic search and data navigation engine has also been developed, covering most aspects of the currently available datasets in the repository. In the next stages, with the growth of deposited data, the search engine will be significantly expanded to allow simpler identification of relevant datasets based on various query criteria, including interactive selection of georeferenced datasets on a world map.

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3. The BIOcean5D Data Hub - a sharing platform and connecting node

In the BIOcean5D project, a strategic approach to data management is implemented, distinguishing - where possible - between raw and derived data types to optimize their storage and accessibility. Raw data, encompassing various fields such as imagery (via EcoTaxa) and acoustics (stored in Zenodo when field-specific repositories are unavailable) or omics, is systematically categorized. Conversely, derived data, including diversity metrics, are integrated into the BIOcean5D data hub, subsequently shared with broader repositories like EurOBIS and EMODnet Biology, which house different data forms, from abundance metrics to geo-referenced outputs (for more information, see D3.1-DMP, chapter 3.2).

Central to BIOcean5D's vision is the consolidation and facilitation of all digital assets within an open-access data hub at EMBL, adhering to global standards in metadata, formatting, and taxonomic references. This approach ensures a seamless transition of data to extensive, long-term repositories like EurOBIS, EMODnet Biology, OBIS and GBIF, leveraging the collective expertise in data standardization, curation, and archiving from partners across trusted international infrastructures.

During its initial phase, particularly before new data from the TREC expedition and related work packages are integrated, BIOcean5D prioritizes the consolidation and standardization of existing datasets. This phase involves partners gathering, unifying, and enhancing data to bolster their respective tasks, making these datasets available through the project's hub. The project ambitiously incorporates a wide array of data, including new and historical time series, various model codes and outputs, and comprehensive observational data for analytical and modeling endeavors.

Furthermore, throughout the project's duration, BIOcean5D partners will not only generate new primary biodiversity observation data but also detailed metadata capturing their interactions with these datasets, including information on legacy and external data sources. WP 1 through 6, adhering to or seeking advice from WP3's guidelines, will channel this invaluable data into the project's hub and designated trusted repositories, ensuring its long-term availability and integrity, as outlined in the project's data flow concept (depicted in Figure 4).

4. The data submission into the hub

Datasets and the related processed data created by the partners are inserted into the repository formatted according to the JSON-LD/schema.org metadata standards. Metadata can be uploaded using the provided tabular templates, or by using an online form for each individual data type (for supported data types and formats, we refer to the D3.1-DMP). Data validation is performed on each uploaded dataset, ensuring data consistency and correct cross-referencing. Smaller datasets (up to a few gigabytes) are uploaded directly via the data hub web interface. For larger datasets, several upload methods are available, from EMBL's Aspera data management system for direct shipping of data stored on portable hard disks.

The submission of data to the Hub will be accompanied by the submission of provenance and contextual metadata. Datasets should be submitted in standard formats, e.g. as Darwin Core Archives. A multi-omics (meta)data template was created by partner EMBL-EBI based on key standards, checklists and other templates from relevant initiatives, e.g. Darwin Core, EMODnet, EBI-ENA, ISA-tab, to use for datasets which can not be fully captured in an existing standard format. A thorough mapping to these other metadata standards is under development. Metadata are submitted as five separate CSV tabular files, or one Excel file with five separate tables, and include mandatory, recommended and optional fields that capture fields that are common to, as well as specific to the different 'omics and environmental data types.

1. The **Author** table provides information about any individual or consortium involved in the production of the data, including their ORCID and their role;
2. The **Classification** table provides information about any organisms, molecules, functions or any classifiable entity used to provide context to the data. It includes Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) from authoritative registries or ontologies such as NCBI taxonomy, ChEBI chemistry, the Gene Ontology, etc. It also includes a mapping between the NCBI and WoRMS taxonomy;
3. The **Record** table provides PIDs and citation fields for any study, sample, or analysis associated with the production of the data;

4. The **Context** table provides metadata about the environment, the event (temporal and spatial dimension), and the methodology used to conduct a study, collect a sample or carry out an analysis;
5. The **Measurement** table contains the data values together with the PIDs of the related studies, samples, analyses and classifications.

Submission is enabled upon registration. As part of this process, the user creates a profile with basic information. This includes a persistent digital identifier, typically ORCID, along with the identifier of the source and the record URL. A mandatory part of author details includes name, email, and affiliation with an institution. Finally, the contribution(s) attribute specifies the role(s) of the user. When submitting the metadata template, these fields can all be left blank if the user details are the same. Otherwise, the **author** table needs to be filled out, and it will be given priority over the user profile data.

The next part is a description of the actual **record**. It generally has two parts: unique identifiers of public data and less formal details about the data. Every record has a title and description in a free text format. The title should clearly capture the nature of the dataset, and the description should contain a narrative describing the curation steps. A more structured description is then provided by a list of keywords. Methods should capture both how the respective sample was collected and the medium of interest (e.g. DNA) extracted, processed, and analyzed. A Creative Commons license and language must be specified for every record. Finally, the identifier of the published record and a reference to its source with a URL links the records to the actual published data. If needed, alternative IDs can be provided, as well as references and citations of additional sources or associated publications.

The **classification** lists identified organisms, molecules, functions or any classifiable objects. Besides database identifiers (such as NCBI taxonomy, Protein Data Bank (PDB), Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI)), and the respective object identifier, it is possible to specify more details—these range from kingdom name to species name, as well as scientific or common names.

The **measurement** table lists any obtained values during the analysis process. It is crucial to link this information to appropriate sample and analysis IDs listed in the record table and classification ID from the classification table. The provided value should be associated with the unit (when applicable), and the measured attribute should be properly annotated.

Finally, providing **context** for the associated sample(s) is also important. This particularly means providing information on when and where the sample was taken and the instruments and protocols used. This is achieved with accurate (local and standard) time and GPS location together with depth, height, and altitude when applicable. The device used for the collection of samples should be specified. It is also crucial to associate these values with a BioSamples ID.

This is the first version; it is possible it will be extended by additional optional metadata attributes or that the existing attributes will be updated in a compatible way. The main reasons for such updates are requests from future data users who might lack some key attributes needed for further analysis of the shared data.

5. Data security and access

The security measures for data protection are described in more detail in the project's data management plan (D3.1-DMP). Within the BIOcean5D data hub, EMBL employs a large-scale file system based on the Quobyte software, with daily snapshots and backed up weekly into a tape-based backup pipeline, ensuring data integrity.

Storing data in this manner not only secures it but also simplifies daily access for users. To manage and safeguard user access, the NFSv4-ACLs policy is a viable strategy. Strengthening data security involves deploying measures like password protection and controlled access to data files, which may range from no access to read-only, read-and-write, or administrator-exclusive permissions.

Within the data hub, dataset access rights are individually defined by the data providers. All dataset downloads are logged, and user accounts are approved centrally by the data management team at EMBL.

Annexes

Table A 1: Data in the BIOcean5D data hub

Data type	WP / Subproject	Data contact / related references	Description	Taxonomy	Category	Location	Temporal range	Temporal resolution	depth range	Licence	Filename(s)	Search vocabulary	Source
TRADITIONAL DATA													
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset1	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Amphipoda	Amphipoda	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Amphipoda_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Amphipoda_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz [README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Amphipoda_abundance_biomass.docx	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset2	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Appendicularia	Appendicularia	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Appendicularia_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Appendicularia_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz [README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Appendicularia_abundance_biomass.docx	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset3	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Chaetognatha	Chaetognatha	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Chaetognatha_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Chaetognatha_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz [README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Chaetognatha_abundance_biomass.docx	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset4	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Coccolithophores	Coccolithophores	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Coccolithophores_abund+biomass_MAREDAT_O'Brien2013_20220722.csv.gz	Biological Oceanography --> Phytoplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome Biological Oceanography --> Traits	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)

AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset5	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Copepoda	Copepoda	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Copepoda_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz</p> <p>ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Copepoda_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Copepoda_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset6	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Diatoms	Diatoms	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Diatoms_abund+biomass_MAREDAT_Leblanc2012_20220722.csv.gz</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Phytoplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome Biological Oceanography --> Traits	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset7	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Dinoflagellates	Dinoflagellates	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Dinoflagellates_abund+biomass_20230203.csv.gz</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Phytoplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome Biological Oceanography --> Traits	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset8	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Euphausiacea	Euphausiacea	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Euphausiacea_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz</p> <p>ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Euphausiacea_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Euphausiacea_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset9	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Foraminifera	Foraminifera	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Foraminifera_abund+biomass_20221126.csv.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Foraminifera_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset10	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Jellyfish	Jellyfish	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Jellyfish_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz</p> <p>ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Jellyfish_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Jellyfish_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	B5D partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)

AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset11	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Ostracoda	Ostracoda	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Ostracoda_abund+biomass_20221220.csv.gz</p> <p>ind-carbon-values AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Ostracoda_ind_carbon_values_20220930.xlsx.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Ostracoda_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset12	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Pteropoda	Pteropoda	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Pteropoda_abund+biomass_20220714.csv.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Pteropoda_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset13	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	Thaliacea	Thaliacea	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>abundance and biomass data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_Thaliacea_abund+biomass_Clerc&al_20220922.csv.gz</p> <p>[README] abundance and biomass data [README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_Thaliacea_abundance_biomass.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset14	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	phytoplankton	phytoplankton	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>species-occurrences data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_phytoplankton_species_occurrences_PhytoBasev1_20200313.csv.gz</p> <p>AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_phytoplankton_species_occurrences_PhytoBasev2_2020905.csv.gz</p> <p>[README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_phytoplankton_species_occurrences_PhytoBasev2.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Phytoplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome Biological Oceanography --> Traits	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)
AtlantECO-BASE-v1-Dataset15	WP3	meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch	zooplankton	zooplankton	Data set	Global	Historic (multiple years)	Individual sampling dates	Depth resolved	CC-BY-4.0	<p>species-occurrences data AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_zooplankton_species_occurrences_ZooBasev1_20210714.csv.gz</p> <p>AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_zooplankton_species_occurrences_ZooBasev2_2020909.csv.gz</p> <p>[README] AtlantECO_WP2_microbiome_traditional_zooplankton_species_occurrences_20210714.docx</p> <p>[README] AtlantECO_WP2_traditional_microscopy_zooplankton_species_occurrences_ZooBasev2.docx</p>	Biological Oceanography --> Zooplankton Biological Oceanography --> Microbiome	BSD partners --> ETHZ Other --> global data depositories Other --> Multiple (data synthesis)